

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

**Report on freshwater fluxes from surface mass budget and
sub-shelf melt in Antarctica**

Deliverable D3.2

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History of changes

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1	31 July 2024	First version delivered to the European Commission.	As listed on the second page.
2	10 October 2024	<p>Revision after the 1st EC review, comments of the reviewers have been addressed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Section 1 has been slightly amended. 2) Section 2.2 has been integrated. 3) Section 2.4 has also been integrated with information on the ESGF. 4) Section 3.1: Fig 1 has been replaced with a new one. The text has been integrated with references and explanations. 5) Section 3.3: Text has been added to introduce the new Fig. 6. 6) References have been enhanced with the following: Hansen et al. 2024, Leonard et al. 2011, Mottram et al., Scharcilli et al., Verjans et al. <p>Delivery to the European Commission.</p>	<p>A: Ruth Mottram (DMI)</p> <p>R: C. Bearzotti (DMI)</p>

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1. Publishable summary

Net ice loss from Antarctica is predominantly observed in West Antarctica and the Antarctic Peninsula, with East Antarctica close to a state of balance (Otosaka et al., 2023). The freshwater flux from the continent to the Southern Ocean is driven by solid ice flux, basal melting of ice shelves, and the loss of surface snow and ice by melt and runoff and the wind driven erosion of snow. This deliverable is a report on work carried out in work package 3 of OCEAN:ICE and focuses on the processes that lead to freshwater fluxes from Antarctica at the present day, primarily the runoff of surface melt water, wind driven erosion of surface snow and ice shelf basal melting. Antarctica is notable for very few in-situ observations, therefore we use new state-of-the-art regional climate simulations, including new parameterisations and data assimilation to calculate surface freshwater fluxes over the historical reanalysis period. We also include some insights on observed basal melting of ice shelves from observations with in-situ autonomous phase sensitive radar (ApRES) to assist in assessing satellite based estimates of ice shelf melt and discuss how these observations can be used in evaluating and assimilation into numerical models.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Context and background

There are several processes by which the Antarctic ice sheet (AIS) adds fresh water to the Southern Ocean, balancing the snow accumulation on the ice sheet, which is estimated to total approximately 2500 Gt per year (Mottram *et al.*, 2021). The dominating (primary) freshwater fluxes are iceberg calving from the fronts of ice shelves, the floating extensions of the ice sheet, and melting at the base of these ice shelves. These processes are estimated to be comparable in magnitude and each in the order of 1000-1400 Gt per year (Depoorter *et al.*, 2013; Rignot *et al.*, 2013). Increased basal melting has been associated with the thinning of ice shelves and the resulting acceleration of grounded glaciers that feed these ice shelves (Paolo *et al.*, 2015; Pritchard *et al.*, 2012), notably in the Amundsen Sea sector of West Antarctica (Rignot *et al.*, 2019), and the western coasts of the Antarctic Peninsula (Wouters *et al.*, 2015), leading to AIS mass loss and sea level rise. Freshwater flux to the Southern Ocean from basal melting is one of the topics of this report.

There are three lesser known, secondary fluxes of fresh water from Antarctica. The first one is subglacial melt by geothermal/deformational heat underneath the grounded ice sheet, previously estimated at 65 Gt per year based on modelling (Pattyn, 2010). Another, as of yet unquantified secondary freshwater flux from Antarctica is surface meltwater runoff, which has been observed as e.g. water falling from the edge of Nansen ice shelf in Victoria Land (Bell *et al.*, 2017) and as tidally-induced drainage of meltwater lakes on Amery ice shelf (Trusel *et al.*, 2022). Yet another secondary freshwater source from Antarctica is blowing snow that is transported by the wind from the ice sheet margin onto the ocean/sea ice (Lawrence *et al.*, 2023). In this deliverable report, we also address the latter two fluxes. An updated estimate of subglacial melt at the ice/bedrock interface is provided in Deliverable 3.3, while solid ice flux is dealt with in considerable detail in Deliverable 3.1.

2.2 Surface freshwater export from the Antarctic ice sheet

The Antarctic climate is much colder than e.g. that of the Greenland ice sheet, and as a result the AIS surface melt rates are typically an order of magnitude smaller (Van den Broeke *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, a significant fraction of the meltwater is expected to refreeze when it percolates into the cold firn layer, although ponding of meltwater has been widely observed in all parts of the AIS (Antarctic Peninsula,

West and East Antarctica), mainly on the flat, floating ice shelves (Kingslake *et al.*, 2017; Van Wessem *et al.*, 2023). Also, englacial meltwater storage has been observed in the form of englacial lakes in Dronning Maud Land (Lenaerts *et al.*, 2016) and perennial firn aquifers in the western Antarctic Peninsula (Van Wessem *et al.*, 2021). In addition to runoff, Antarctica can contribute freshwater to the Southern Ocean through snowdrift. Wind and sublimation can deposit and erode snow at magnitudes significantly larger than local precipitation (Scarchilli *et al.* 2009) and this process, while understudied on the ice sheet itself, is important for snowpack development on ice floes (Leonard and Maksym, 2017) and therefore likely also on the meteoric ice.

Owing to the complexity of these processes involved, including vertical/horizontal routing of meltwater and storage, the flux of surface meltwater runoff and snowdrift from the Antarctic ice sheet has to date not yet been quantified. Here we provide a first-order estimate based on modelled surface melt, runoff, and drift. We use output of three state-of-the-art regional climate models (RCMs), which have shown reasonable performance in simulating melt in Greenland: MAR v. 3.10 (Agosta *et al.*, 2019), HIRHAM v.5 (Hansen *et al.*, 2021) and RACMO versions 2.3p2, (Van Wessem *et al.*, 2018) and 2.4p1 (Van Dalum *et al.*, submitted). MAR 3.10 and RACMO 2.4p1 are used to model snowdrift. We estimate total melt, rain, and runoff (melt + rain – refreezing) by summing magnitudes at all coastal cells in each model. We estimate blowing snow magnitudes from MAR 3.10 and RACMO 2.4p1 by summing coastal cells modulated by wind direction. In addition, and in collaboration with the Horizon 2020 project PolarRES, we expect to add two more regional climate models, MetUM and HCLIMcy43 in the coming months as data become available, also for future projections. As a result of the scarcity of in situ melt rate observations, which requires sufficiently accurate radiation measurements to capture the intermittent melt at the AIS surface (Jakobs *et al.*, 2020), evaluation of these models for Antarctic melt rates has been limited to liquid water presence and/or AWS-calibrated seasonal melt totals from active satellite radar (Kuipers Munneke *et al.*, 2012; Trusel *et al.*, 2013).

2.3 Ice shelf basal melting

Basal melting of ice shelves is an important process to monitor as these floating parts of the ice sheet buttress the inland ice and help control discharge into the southern ocean (e.g. Pritchard *et al.*, 2012; First *et al.*, 2016). Erosion and thinning of the shelves from below weakens them and can lead to their abrupt break-up for example, during extreme weather events (Hanna *et al.*, 2024). However, the difficulty of accessing ice shelf cavities, and directly observing melt means that we are dependent on earth observation to assess large scale basal melt patterns (e.g. Adsumili *et al.*, 2020). In this report we also examine in-situ data from ApRES made available to the whole glaciological community via the SOOS approved NECKLACE project (<https://necklaceproject.com/about/>).

2.4 Open Science

The datasets described in this deliverable are accessible to all project partners via the OCEAN:ICE data server. Regional Climate Model data will be published on Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) servers as part of Polar CORDEX by the end of 2024. Due to the distributed nature of the ESGF, the location of the different models may differ, but full instructions for accessing data will be reported in the data report on zenodo (in the PolarRES community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/polarres>) as well as in the experimental protocol (Mottram *et al.*, submitted.). More specialised surface mass balance outputs are already available on application to the authors of this report and will be uploaded to online repositories [Zenodo](#) and [OpenAire](#) when papers currently in preparation have been accepted for publication.

3. Results

3.1 Meltwater extent and runoff

First we provide an upper estimate of AIS runoff by assuming all meltwater that is modelled at the surface to run off, i.e. refreezing and liquid water retention in the firn are assumed zero. Table 1 shows the modelled total AIS integrated 1979-2022 average values of melt, runoff and rain (in Gt yr⁻¹), partitioned into regional contributions from East Antarctica, West Antarctica and the Antarctic Peninsula), and Figs. 1a-c maps of the average specific values (in kg m⁻² yr⁻¹). These numbers represent 3.3%, 4.9% and 25.2% of the freshwater flux from solid ice discharge over the grounding line, if we assume the latter to equal average snow accumulation (~2550 Gt yr⁻¹). This confirms that the inter-RCM differences in AIS melt rate are very large (Carter *et al.*, 2022), much larger than for e.g. the Greenland ice sheet (Mankoff *et al.*, 2021). This can be ascribed to the lack of in situ melt rate observations to calibrate the models with and the fact that the intermittent nature of AIS melt makes modelled values very sensitive to the snowmelt-albedo feedback, which can locally double the melt rate (Jakobs *et al.*, 2021). Still, this is insufficient to fully explain the large (factor eight) difference between the RCMs with least (MAR) and most (HIRHAM) melt. In light of the scant (satellite-based) melt estimates (Trusel *et al.*, 2013), we surmise that the HIRHAM melt rates are overestimates. On the other hand, statistical downscaling of the RACMO melt to a 2 km resolution suggests that the MAR and RACMO values are probably underestimates, not properly resolving the highest melt rates in topographically steep terrain, e.g. close to the ice sheet grounding line where melt is known to peak (Lenaerts *et al.*, 2016; Noel *et al.*, 2023). Some overestimation of melt from HIRHAM under some circumstances can be attributed to cloud parameterisations that affect the partitioning of water and ice content in clouds (Hansen *et al.*, 2024).

Fig. 1 (previous page): Average (1979-2022) annual totals ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ or mm w.e. yr^{-1}) of melt (upper row), runoff (second row) and rain (third row) in MAR (left column), RACMO (middle column) and HIRHAM (right column). Lowest row shows average annual total drifting snow transport ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) for MAR (1979-2022) and RACMO (1999-2013). Note: RACMO version 2p3 used for snowdrift ($27 \times 27 \text{ km}^2$), RACMO 2p4 ($11 \times 11 \text{ km}^2$) used for melt, runoff, and rain.

The three RCMs also provide direct estimates of runoff (Table 1), as they are equipped with multi-layered snow schemes capable of simulating percolation, capillary retention and refreezing of liquid water. In the current model versions, runoff is assumed to occur if liquid water reaches the firn-ice interface, i.e. no lateral water motion is explicitly simulated. This implies that inter-model differences in runoff are expected to be even more significant than in melt, because in addition to the differences in liquid water input (melt plus rain) as described above, runoff also depends strongly on the model treatment of subsurface processes. The contribution of rain to the total liquid water input $\text{rain}/(\text{melt}+\text{rain})$ varies from 2.3% (RACMO), 5.9% (HIRHAM) to 16% (MAR). The fraction of liquid water available at the AIS surface that is retained in the firn by refreezing and retention $(\text{melt}+\text{rain}-\text{runoff})/(\text{melt}+\text{rain})$ varies from 76% (HIRHAM), 86% (MAR), to 96% (RACMO). This results in modelled runoff rates that differ even stronger than the melt rates, by a factor of 28 between RACMO (least) and HIRHAM (most). There is currently no objective way to favour either of these predictions. Hansen et al., (2020) show that retention and refreezing in models is very sensitive to factors such as snow pack initialisation and layer dynamical schemes as well as snow parameterisation, unfortunately we have very little data to be able to distinguish between these. Analysis by Verjans et al., (2021) and in Mottram et al. (2021) suggest that there are large regional variations in representation of SMB and SMB components.

		MAR	RACMO ^a	HIRHAM
Melt	AIS	84	124	509
	AP	56	58	166
	WAIS	5.4	11	136
	EAIS	22	55	206
Rain	AIS	16	2.9	32
	AP	13	2.4	6.4
	WAIS	1.2	0.4	8.4
	EAIS	1.3	0.1	17
Runoff	AIS	14	4.8	132
	AP	12	3.4	82
	WAIS	0.0	0.0	7.6
	EAIS	2.4	1.4	43
Drifting snow	AIS	31	6.7	
	AP	8.3	0.2	
	WAIS	11.2	1.1	
	EAIS	11.5	5.4	

Table 1: AIS integrated (using the native model ice mask and including the ice shelves) annual melt, runoff and rain. All values reported in gigatonnes per year (Gt yr^{-1}). To obtain these climatological averages, daily or

monthly totals were summed to annual totals and averaged across the same 24-year time slice for all models (Jan 1979 - Dec 2022).

^a RACMO 2p3 used for snowdrift (27 x 27 km²), RACMO 2p4 (11 x 11 km²) used for melt, runoff, and rain.

3.2 Drifting snow transport over the edge of the Antarctic ice sheet

Owing to the highly persistent and strong katabatic winds that are forced by a combination of surface radiative cooling and - away from the ice domes - the presence of a surface slope, drifting and blowing snow are very common phenomena in Antarctica. With depths occasionally reaching up to several hundreds of metres, the blowing snow layer is even observable from space using satellite laser altimetry (Palm *et al.*, 2017). As of yet, it has not been quantified how much freshwater leaves the continent in the form of drifting/blowing snow that is transported over the edge of the ice sheet. Two of the RCMs in this study, MAR (Amory *et al.*, 2021) and RACMO2.4p1 (Gadde and van de Berg, 2024) have drifting snow routines. The drifting snow routine in RACMO2.4p1 replaces the previous version which for the average gave reasonable results (Lenaerts and Van den Broeke, 2012; Lenaerts *et al.*, 2012) but contained an error by failing to integrate over all relevant particle size classes. This was revealed by comparing the old and new schemes to long-term in situ observations of drifting and blowing snow flux at site D47 in Adélie Land (Amory, 2020), see Fig. 2. The same observations have been used to assess the quality of the modelled drifting snow fluxes in MAR (Amory *et al.*, 2021). In both models there is also qualitative good agreement between depth of the blowing snow layer with satellite laser altimetry (Palm *et al.*, 2017).

Fig. 2: Improved performance of the drifting snow scheme in RACMO2.4p1 vs. previous model version, by using a direct comparison with in situ observations from site D47 in Adélie Land, East Antarctica. From (Gadde and van de Berg, 2024).

Figure 2 (lowest row) shows average annual drifting snow fluxes for MAR and RACMO (in kg m⁻¹ yr⁻¹). The patterns look broadly similar, although some significant differences can also be seen, e.g. in the western Antarctic Peninsula. In general, MAR predicts about twice higher drifting snow fluxes compared to RACMO. Relevant for this study is how much drifting snow is blown over the edge of the ice mask into the ocean. This flux is obtained by summing all drifting snow transport in coastal grid cells that is directed offshore (defined as drifting snow transport directed from an ice covered to an ocean cell). For this first application we do not partition how much of this freshwater flux ends up on (land fast) sea ice (Lawrence *et al.*, 2023) or in open water. The results in Table 1 show that, interestingly, this freshwater flux is larger than the runoff in both models by approximately a factor of two. MAR predicts a five times larger blowing snow freshwater flux than RACMO, with differences especially significant over the Antarctic Peninsula (factor 40) but better agreement for the East Antarctic ice sheet (factor two). The HIRHAM5 regional climate model does not include snow drift

erosion, analysis shown in Figure 3 of the sublimation and evaporation at the surface, calculated also using modelled wind fields, suggests that these components of mass loss are comparable with ice loss due to runoff in the same model. As Mottram et al (2021) also show, these figures for sublimation and evaporation related mass loss are consistent within an order of magnitude across the different RCMs available in the Polar CORDEX archive.

Fig. 3: Annual mean runoff and evaporation and sublimation fluxes calculated over the whole ice sheet with the HIRHAM5 regional climate model.

Although it is too early to provide robust absolute numbers based on these model experiments, these new results do imply that freshwater fluxes from surface runoff and blowing snow are likely significant, with upper estimates (neglecting retention) up to 5-20% of the solid ice discharge. In the case of runoff, this fraction will rapidly increase in a warmer future climate, estimates of which will be reported in the course of the project.

3.3 Ice shelf basal melting

Data from 10 different nations operating in Antarctica have been used to build a common dataset of ice shelf basal melting in the NECKLACE database. This database will be available online shortly via the NECKLACE website and is already available to OCEAN:ICE project partners working in task 3.3. As a new publication Mottram et al (Accepted), based on the Earth Observation workshop presented in the milestone MS6 report on “Workshop with ESA CCI and EO on ice shelf mass balance (MS6)” (<https://zenodo.org/records/8033778>) shows, there is significant disagreement between in-situ measurements of ice shelf basal melt and those derived from Earth Observation and this therefore has been a key task within WP3 to resolve.

Fig. 4: Map showing in-situ observations of ice shelf basal melting available in the NECKLACE database as visualised using the SOOS map.

This mismatch is highlighted in Figure 5 (created with data from Adsumilli et al., 2020 and Vaňková and Nicholls, 2022) where neither the spatial distribution of basal melting, nor the temporal variability are particularly well captured. Sources of mismatch between these datasets may include the different timescales of processes observed, differing assumptions about ice shelf strain rates and the use of regional climate model derived accumulation rates within the processing data.

Fig. 5: (top) shows basal ice shelf melt over the Ronne-Filchner ice shelf derived by satellite data from Adsumilli et al., 2020. The round circles show ice shelf melt rates derived from in-situ ApRES data (published by Vankova and Nicholls, 2022). bottom shows the temporal variability Basal melt rate time series derived from in-situ measurements (red) compared with estimates from satellite data; the quarter-yearly satellite estimates (black) and their low-pass filtered (blue) version as in Adusumilli et al. (2020). Both figures taken from Vaňková

and Nicholls, 2022.

The ApRES data is a point observation, as opposed to the gridded area data from Earth Observation, which is one of the reasons it is hard to compare the two types of observations. The observational period also has a much higher frequency of measurement, as the plot in Figure 6 shows. These kind of high frequency point measurements can be challenging to use for model evaluation, but techniques to assimilate such datasets, as for example used in numerical weather prediction models, are widespread. The iENKS algorithm developed in Task 3. 4 and reported in MS 8 can therefore also be used to assimilate the ApRES datasets into the ocean-ice coupled model. This has never previously been attempted and the results are therefore uncertain at this stage but will be included in D3.4.

Fig 6. Time series plot of ice shelf basal thinning rate from KOPRI site AR06 on Thwaites Main Trunk, close to the grounding zone. The data from this site indicate that it went from partially grounded to fully floating during the two-year deployment.

Given the documented high temporal variability of ocean driven melting under ice shelves, it is important to collect and analyse long time series of data to better understand how EO derived datasets can best be evaluated with in-situ datasets (Cook et al., 2023). Apart from using the ApRES derived point observations of basal thinning for validation of EO derived melt rates melt rates and assimilation of melt rates in model runs, there is potential to invert these datasets to evaluate SMB and firn density models. The ApRES data measures the changes in the thickness of the ice shelf. Some of these changes are related to basal melting, but changes in the upper layers are related to snow fall accumulation and density. Inverting the outputs to derive density changes in the upper layers will help to derive both accumulation and densification parameters that can be used to distinguish between model outputs. A publication in preparation is therefore now also examining the role of surface processes and specifically regional climate model outputs that are used in EO data processing to derive melt rates. This is a good example of the synergies that OCEAN:ICE - a wide project with diverse partners is able to develop. Data from both EO data and ApRES is now in a format that is ready to be used in Task 3.3.

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4. Impact

This deliverable contributes directly to the following objectives listed in the Description of the Action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica.

D3.2 focuses on the loss of ice to the southern ocean by atmospheric and ocean processes, specifically by using in-situ observations from ApRES to assess Earth Observation derived datasets on ice shelf basal melt rates.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models.

D3.2 has implemented new process in regional climate models used to assess accumulation, melt, runoff, sublimation and wind driven erosion of snow. These insights will be used later in T3.3.

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet-climate models.

The data from the RCMs described in this deliverable report are a direct input to ice sheet and coupled climate models used in WP4 as well as in later parts of WP3.

O4: Quantify AIS melt sensitivity to climate forcing and reduce the ‘deep uncertainty’ in freshwater flux and SLR projections to 2300.

D3.2 shows the importance of including wind driven snow processes into climate models, and quantifies the uncertainty in modelled melt from regional climate models by comparing 3 different models.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

D3.2 does not contribute to this objective.

O6: Assess the ocean impact on key global climate metrics from polar ice sheet melt to 2300 and beyond.

D3.2 contributes to this objective by supplying freshwater fluxes from surface and ice shelf basal processes to other parts of the OCEAN:ICE consortium.

O7: Deliver free and open data access and contribute to international assessments, climate model development, observing initiatives and policymakers.

All datasets developed in D3.2 are freely available to the consortium and will be published open access once publications in preparation have been accepted.